

Attitudes of Researchers to Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands: Survey Results

Lena Ryzhova¹

^{1,2}MA Book and Digital Media Studies, Leiden University and
Erasmus University Rotterdam

¹[olenaryzova@gmail.com]; ²[bibbi.siviero@gmail.com]

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Executive Summary

This report explores how researchers in the Netherlands perceive Diamond Open Access (DOA), a publishing model that provides free access to readers and does not charge authors. The study, conducted within the *Strengthening Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands* program, surveyed researchers across disciplines and career stages, with a particular focus on early-career academics.

Findings reveal that while many researchers are open to the idea of DOA, awareness remains uneven – especially in STEM fields and among early-career scholars. Decisions about where to publish are still largely driven by journal reputation, visibility, and institutional expectations. Humanities and social sciences researchers appear more receptive to DOA, particularly for books, whereas researchers in other fields express concern over recognition and career impact. Interview insights further emphasize that without institutional support – such as funding, indexing, and recognition in evaluation processes – DOA will remain a niche option. While current initiatives are promising, sustained efforts are needed to increase awareness, improve infrastructure, and embed DOA within academic culture and reward systems.

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Introduction

In recent years, the Diamond Open Access (DOA) model has gained increasing attention as a promising next step in the evolution of scholarly publishing. Unlike other Open Access models, DOA publishers provide free access to readers, and do not charge publishing fees to authors or their institutions. This model is seen as a potential way to further disentangle academic publishing from the commercial interests of large publishing corporations. However, because DOA relies on funding from grants and institutional support – such as libraries, consortia and universities – it requires strong community backing. Central to this support are researchers themselves, who ultimately need to be willing to publish through DOA outlets for the model to succeed and scale.

In the Netherlands, several significant initiatives have been launched to support and advance the DOA publishing model. Of particular note is the *Strengthening Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands* program, coordinated by the partnership of the University Libraries and National Library (UKB, 2024), which comprises three sub-projects: the development of infrastructures for DOA, the mapping and monitoring of DOA initiatives in the Netherlands, and the establishment of a national Diamond Open Access Expertise Center. In parallel, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) has introduced a separate funding scheme to support the flipping of existing journals to the DOA model (NWO, 2024). While these initiatives have been in place for some time, actual data on how well they reach researchers, and how DOA is perceived by its key audience, has been lacking until now. Researchers are central to the scholarly communication ecosystem as producers of research, reviewers, editors and readers. Their engagement and perspectives are crucial for the long-term success and sustainability of DOA. This survey aims to fill that gap. It provides insight into the current attitudes toward DOA among researchers based in the Netherlands. We inquired into their general publishing habits and preferences, with a particular focus on early-career researchers who often face greater pressure to publish in prestigious, high-impact journals.

Surveys on researchers' publishing preferences have been conducted in various contexts. Rowley et al. (2022) found that journal selection is mainly driven by peer review reliability, quality of reviewer feedback, journal reputation, and scope fit – factors consistent across disciplines and career stages. Johann et al. (2024) showed that publication strategies vary by discipline and career level, with high pressure leading researchers to prioritize reputation, speed, and international reach over Open Access or local relevance. In this survey, we focus specifically on the Dutch academic landscape, investigating researchers' publishing preferences and perceptions of Diamond Open Access across different disciplines and career stages. Originally, the survey was designed to target early career researchers, however, due to the expected composition of our survey respondents, it was decided that the questions would address researchers at all career stages, with a slight emphasis on the needs and perspectives of younger scholars. Our findings aim to contribute to the ongoing conversation about the role and future of DOA in the Netherlands.

Methodology and Limitations

This study was conducted as part of a research internship within the UKB program *Strengthening Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands*. The primary aim was to better understand researchers' awareness, experiences and perceptions of DOA publishing, with a particular focus on early-career scholars. While the focus of the project was specific to the Dutch academic landscape, the survey design drew inspiration from previous studies on publishing behaviour, including the Taylor & Francis Open Access survey (2013), which informed the structure and phrasing of several questions.

The survey consisted of three sections. The first gathered general background information about respondents, including their disciplinary affiliation and career stage. The second section explored respondents' publishing habits and familiarity with open access models more broadly. The third section focused specifically on DOA, asking about respondents' attitudes, experiences, and perceived challenges or motivators related to publishing through this model (for the full survey questionnaire see Appendix 1).

The survey was open for approximately six weeks. To reach a broad audience, a diverse distribution strategy was employed: the survey was shared publicly via LinkedIn and disseminated through university channels with the help of subject librarians and faculty liaisons. PhD students and early-career researchers were also contacted directly via email where possible. Additional outreach was carried out through the UKB network, with more focused dissemination in institutions where the research team had established contacts or where program supervisors were based, including Utrecht University, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Leiden University, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and the Open University.

To deepen the insights gathered from the survey, six semi-structured interviews were conducted with researchers who had expressed interest in further participation by leaving their contact information at the end of the questionnaire. These interviews were held online or in person and offered qualitative perspectives on publishing choices and attitudes toward DOA.

While the survey provided valuable insights, several limitations must be acknowledged. Despite broad outreach efforts, no responses were received from a number of Dutch universities, including Wageningen University, the University of Twente, the University of Groningen, Maastricht University and Eindhoven University of Technology. As a result, the findings should not be considered nationally representative and may reflect institutional or field-related biases linked to where dissemination efforts were most effective. Due to time constraints, we did not survey or interview researchers at Universities of Applied Sciences (*Hogescholen*), although we recognize that research and publishing are becoming increasingly important in these practice-based institutions as well.

Another key limitation concerns the distribution of career stages among respondents. Although the project aimed to focus on early-career researchers, the final sample included a large

proportion of established academics, such as associate and full professors. While their perspectives are undoubtedly important, the views of PhD students and postdoctoral researchers – groups likely to face different pressures and considerations in their publishing choices – were comparatively underrepresented. Efforts were made to address this imbalance by directly targeting PhD candidates, but the response rate remained lower than anticipated.

In addition, although the survey offered respondents the opportunity to participate in follow-up interviews, time and logistical constraints limited the number of interviews that could be conducted. This restricted the depth of qualitative insight that could be added to the survey findings.

Taken together, these limitations highlight the need for further research, ideally on a larger scale and with targeted strategies for reaching underrepresented institutions and career groups. Such efforts would help build a more comprehensive understanding of how DOA is perceived and supported across the full spectrum of the Dutch research community.

Findings

This survey was completed by researchers from a diverse range of Dutch universities, with particularly strong representation from Erasmus University Rotterdam, Utrecht University, Leiden University and Tilburg University (Figure 1). Respondents represented various career stages, including PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, and senior academics such as associate and full professors (Figure 2). The survey also captured a broad mix of academic disciplines, notably humanities, social sciences, engineering, computer science and AI (Figure 3). Most participants had published at least one academic work, ensuring their responses reflect direct experience with scholarly publishing (Figure 4). This wide diversity in background and expertise provides a rich foundation for understanding perspectives on DOA publishing across fields and career stages.

The results reveal a complex landscape of motivations, barriers, and awareness surrounding DOA publishing among researchers in the Netherlands. While 57% of respondents reported being familiar with DOA prior to the survey, a significant portion, 24%, had never heard of it, and 19% were unsure. This highlights a persistent awareness gap within the academic community, particularly among early-career researchers and those in STEM fields. Key factors shaping publication choices include journal reputation, peer-review quality, and cost, while common barriers to DOA adoption center on concerns about visibility, sustainability, and the pressure to publish in high-impact venues. Despite these challenges, a significant number of researchers expressed openness to considering DOA publishing, especially if supported by institutional guidance and dedicated funding. These insights are discussed in detail in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, which combine visual data and interpretive analysis to offer a comprehensive view of the current attitudes and experiences related to DOA across the Dutch academic community.

Figure 1. Respondents by university affiliation

Figure 2. Respondents by current academic position

Figure 3. Respondents by field of research

Figure 4. Number of publications per respondent, including books and articles

To provide a more detailed and comparative analysis, the following section breaks down survey findings by career stage – distinguishing early-career researchers (research master's students, PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers) from senior academics (assistant, associate, and full

professors) – as well as by disciplinary grouping: social sciences, humanities and STEM. All survey data will be made available on Zenodo alongside this report, with any potentially identifying information removed to ensure anonymity. In addition, graphs corresponding to each survey question – disaggregated by career stage and disciplinary field – are provided in Appendix 2 for reference and further analysis.

General Awareness and Publishing in Diamond Open Access Venues

When looking at general awareness of Diamond Open Access, a clear trend emerges: senior researchers tend to be more familiar with DOA, likely reflecting their broader experience with academic publishing. However, disciplinary differences are also significant. For instance, early-career researchers in the humanities (Figure 5) displayed greater awareness of DOA than senior researchers in STEM (Figure 6). In fact, awareness among early-career researchers in STEM was the lowest overall, with only 32% reporting confidence in their knowledge of the model.

Figure 5. Awareness of the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)" among early-career researchers in the humanities

Figure 6. Awareness of the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)" among senior researchers in STEM fields

A lack of familiarity with DOA appears to correlate with perceptions of its suitability for early-career researchers. Only 42% of senior researchers in STEM agreed that DOA is a suitable option for early-career academics (Figure 7), compared to 75% in the humanities (Figure 8). This may be due to the greater emphasis placed on impact factor and journal reputation in STEM fields, where DOA journals are perceived to lack comparable prestige. This interpretation was supported during an interview with a senior STEM researcher, who acknowledged that while there is broad ideological support for Open Access, few early-career scholars would risk publishing in journals that might not be recognized in hiring or promotion decisions.

Figure 7. Perceptions of DOA as a suitable option for early-career researchers — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 8. Perceptions of DOA as a suitable option for early-career researchers — senior researchers in the humanities

When asked about the factors that influence decisions to publish in a DOA journal or book, the majority of STEM respondents reported little or no prior experience with DOA publishing. Those who had engaged with it cited journal or publisher reputation and recognition, as well as the absence of article processing charges (APCs) and book processing charges (BPCs), as key motivations (Figures 9 and 10). In the social sciences and humanities, the absence of APCs and BPCs was also identified as a major factor, along with reputation (Figures 11, 12, 13). Notably, early-career researchers in the humanities also emphasized the importance of inclusion in indexing databases and library catalogues (Figure 14). Interviews with researchers in the fields of Philosophy and Law further highlighted these considerations.

Figure 9. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 10. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — early-career researchers in STEM

Figure 11. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — senior researchers in the social sciences

Figure 12. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — early-career researchers in the social sciences

Figure 13. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — senior researchers in the humanities

Figure 14. Factors influencing DOA publishing decisions — early-career researchers in the humanities

To better understand hesitations around DOA publishing, respondents were asked to select barriers specific to journals and books. For journal publishing, senior researchers in the social sciences cited expectations to publish in well-established or high-impact journals, preference for journals with high impact factors, and concerns about journal visibility and recognition as primary concerns (Figure 15). These concerns were similarly reflected among senior STEM researchers, the majority of whom selected concerns about visibility and recognition as their top barrier (Figure 16). In contrast, senior researchers in the humanities highlighted a lack of institutional support or funding as one of the most pressing issues (Figure 17). These findings were echoed in interviews, where multiple researchers emphasized that DOA currently lacks the name recognition and prestige associated with traditional or APC-based Open Access models. Some participants also noted that DOA options simply do not exist in their specific subfields. Among early-career researchers, similar concerns were voiced, particularly in the social sciences and humanities, where a lack of awareness about DOA options was frequently mentioned (Figures 18 and 19).

Figure 15. Perceived barriers to publishing in DOA journals — senior researchers in the social sciences

Figure 16. Perceived barriers to publishing in DOA journals — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 17. Perceived barriers to publishing in DOA journals — senior researchers in the humanities

Figure 18. Perceived barriers to publishing in DOA journals — early-career researchers in the social sciences

Figure 19. Perceived barriers to publishing in DOA journals — early-career researchers in the humanities

Regarding book publishing, overall response rates were lower, especially among STEM respondents, as publishing monographs or edited collections is less common in those disciplines. Among senior researchers, the most cited barriers were concerns about the long-term sustainability of DOA publishing infrastructure and the limited availability of DOA publishers in their field (Figure 20). Early-career respondents, in contrast, were most concerned with the visibility and reach of DOA books (Figure 21). In the humanities and social sciences, where books are central to scholarly output and often crucial for career progression, respondents identified a variety of barriers. These included a lack of awareness about DOA book publishing options, preference for established or traditional publishers, and concerns about sustainability (Figure 22). Among early-career researchers, the most frequently cited factor was lack of awareness.

Figure 20. Perceived barriers to publishing books in a DOA model — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 21. Perceived barriers to publishing books in a DOA model — early-career researchers in STEM

Figure 22. Perceived barriers to publishing books in a DOA model — senior researchers in the social sciences

A postdoc in communication science pointed out that in her field, visibility is the main currency of value, and many colleagues are skeptical of Open Access models. She added that awareness about DOA is limited unless one actively seeks it out, and a curated list of reputable DOA journals by discipline would be a useful tool. Similarly, an associate professor in STEM noted that while DOA options exist in his field, their visibility is low. He emphasized the need for better branding, indexing, and policy-level change, stating that only strong policies will actually shift publishing behaviors.

In response to the question of whether respondents would consider using DOA venues if their university provided support, the majority agreed that institutional backing would make them more likely to publish in a DOA model. However, STEM researchers showed the highest rate of neutrality or resistance to changing their publishing habits, even with institutional support (Figures 23 and 24). When asked what resources would help them decide whether to publish in a DOA venue, respondents frequently selected institutional policies supporting DOA, more funding for DOA publications and toolkits offering clear guidance. Early-career researchers additionally noted the importance of mentorship, highlighting the value of guidance from supervisors or senior colleagues (Figure 25). Several interviewees echoed this, stating that without institutional promotion and structural incentives, DOA is unlikely to gain ground in their academic environments.

Figure 23. Consideration of university support for publishing in a DOA journal or book — senior career researchers in STEM

Figure 24. Consideration of university support for publishing in a DOA journal or book — early career researchers in STEM

Figure 25. Support or resources that would help decide whether to publish in a DOA outlet — early career researchers in the social sciences

In conclusion, while attitudes toward DOA vary across disciplines and career stages, many of these differences stem from field-specific publishing cultures – such as the centrality of monographs in the humanities or the weight placed on impact factors in STEM. Researchers’ choices are shaped by a combination of practical considerations (such as visibility, indexing and funding), career pressures and institutional norms. Despite current barriers, there is a clear openness among researchers, particularly early-career ones, to consider DOA publishing, provided there is sufficient institutional support, clearer guidance and access to reputable outlets.

Publishing Experience and Habits

To better understand the context in which researchers operate and make publishing decisions, one section of the survey focused on questions exploring researchers’ publishing experiences and habits. To set the stage, respondents were first asked about the degree of freedom they have when choosing where to publish. Among senior researchers, the highest percentage of those reporting ‘complete freedom’ was found in STEM fields (Figure 26). In contrast, in the humanities and social sciences, only around 33% of respondents reported full freedom, with the remainder indicating that they had some freedom but faced recommendations or expectations (Figures 27 and 28). Early-career researchers reported a very different situation. In this group, only 31% of humanities researchers reported complete freedom (Figure 29), followed by 20% in the social sciences (Figure 30), and just 9% in STEM fields (Figure 31). Across all disciplines, it is evident that early-career researchers rarely enjoy full autonomy in their publishing decisions, often due to pressures related to tenure, funding, or career progression.

Figure 26. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 27. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — senior researchers in the social sciences

Figure 28. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — senior researchers in the humanities

Figure 29. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — early career researchers in the humanities

Figure 30. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — early career researchers in the social sciences

Figure 31. Freedom in choosing where to publish research — early career researchers in STEM

In some cases, external constraints further limit this freedom. One respondent, for example, noted that if a journal has an impact factor below 3, they cannot use institutional Open Access funds to

cover APCs. Another researcher in the field of law mentioned a controversial curated list of ‘recommended journals’ that circulated within their faculty. However, there are exceptions. One interviewed humanities researcher stated a strong preference for publishing only in Diamond Open Access venues, even if this choice risks stagnating their career progression.

Closely related to the question of publishing freedom is whether researchers receive encouragement from their faculty or supervisors to publish in specific journals or with particular book publishers. Among senior researchers, most respondents reported not receiving such guidance. This was especially pronounced in STEM fields, where 65% indicated they had not been encouraged to publish in specific venues, and only 6% reported frequent encouragement (Figure 32). A similar trend appeared in the social sciences, where 59% responded ‘no’ and just 6% said ‘yes, frequently’ (Figure 33). The humanities showed a more balanced picture: 46% reported no encouragement, while 38% had received occasional suggestions (Figure 34). In contrast, early-career researchers reported more frequent guidance from faculty or supervisors regarding where to publish. In the social sciences, 60% said they were occasionally encouraged to publish in specific outlets, with 10% experiencing frequent guidance (Figure 35). Only 20% reported receiving no such advice. Humanities respondents showed similar patterns, with 50% indicating occasional encouragement and 22% frequent direction from supervisors (Figure 36). In STEM, the distribution was slightly more varied: 47% reported occasional guidance, 14% frequent, and 38% said they had not been encouraged at all (Figure 37).

Figure 32. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — senior researchers in STEM

Figure 33. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — senior researchers in the social sciences

Figure 34. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — senior researchers in the humanities

Figure 35. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — early career researchers in the social sciences

Figure 36. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — early career researchers in the humanities

Figure 37. Encouragement to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers — early career researchers in STEM

These results suggest that while senior researchers might enjoy more autonomy in their publishing decisions, early-career scholars are more likely to be influenced by recommendations or expectations from within their academic environment. This reflects broader patterns of mentorship and institutional culture, where publication strategy is often shaped by disciplinary norms and implicit or explicit guidance from more senior colleagues.

When examining the factors that influence researchers' decisions on where to publish their work, several broad patterns emerge, along with a few notable disciplinary and career-stage differences. For journal publishing, journal reputation and open access availability consistently rank among the most important factors across nearly all groups, regardless of discipline or seniority. However, early-career researchers in STEM placed greater emphasis on impact factors, suggesting that career advancement pressures weigh more heavily on those at the beginning of their academic trajectory (Figure 38). In contrast, early-career researchers in the humanities prioritised special issues relevant to their research, pointing to a strategic approach more aligned with visibility and thematic fit rather than purely metric-based evaluation (Figure 39). Across all groups, recommendations from supervisors or faculty and editorial board invitations were generally rated as the least influential factors, indicating a strong desire for autonomy or at least a perception that such influences carry limited weight in practice.

Figure 38. Importance of factors influencing journal article publishing decisions (average ratings) — early career researchers in STEM

Figure 39. Importance of factors influencing journal article publishing decisions (average ratings) — early career researchers in the humanities

Book publishing showed slightly more variation. Publisher reputation remained the most important factor across all disciplines and career stages, though its significance was complemented by field-specific priorities. In the humanities and social sciences, factors such as open access availability, peer-review quality, and the design and production quality of the book were highly valued (Figure 40, 41). In STEM fields, early-career researchers notably prioritised rights and contracts, perhaps reflecting concern over intellectual property (Figure 42). An important outlier appears among early-career humanities scholars, who placed greater emphasis on affordability and distribution and accessibility – a likely reflection of the centrality of monographs to career development in this field (Figure 43). Unlike their STEM peers, they are more likely to need their work published in accessible and widely distributed book formats, particularly for dissertations or early monographs.

Figure 40. Importance of factors influencing book publishing decisions (average ratings) — senior researchers in the humanities

Figure 41. Importance of factors influencing book publishing decisions (average ratings) — senior researchers in the social sciences

Figure 42. Importance of factors influencing book publishing decisions (average ratings) — early career researchers in STEM

Figure 43. Importance of factors influencing book publishing decisions (average ratings) — early career researchers in the humanities

The presented data suggests that while some factors are universally important (e.g., reputation, open access), career stage and disciplinary publishing cultures strongly shape how researchers evaluate potential venues, particularly when it comes to books. Preferences reflect not only personal priorities but also field-specific norms and career pressures.

Conclusion

This report provides a snapshot of the current attitudes, awareness levels and decision-making practices of researchers in the Netherlands regarding Diamond Open Access publishing. While support for the ideals of DOA is evident, particularly in the form of interest in affordability, equity, and institutional backing, actual engagement with DOA remains limited, especially in fields where journal prestige and impact factor are critical to career advancement. Disciplinary differences are substantial: researchers in the humanities and social sciences appear more open to DOA models, especially for monographs, while STEM researchers show greater scepticism, often tied to concerns about visibility, journal quality and institutional incentives. Early-career researchers are both more vulnerable to these structural pressures and more open to alternative publishing models, in a situation where they receive mentorship, clear guidance, and institutional support.

The findings reinforce the need for a multi-pronged strategy to make Diamond Open Access a more viable and attractive option. Greater awareness must be paired with stronger publishing infrastructure – such as sustainable platforms, indexing systems, and editorial support – as well as clearer institutional policies that actively promote and facilitate DOA publishing. In particular, the role of supervisors, mentors, and university frameworks is crucial in shaping the publishing choices of early-career researchers. Recognition and reward systems also play a key role: researchers are more likely to consider DOA if such venues are acknowledged in hiring, promotion, and funding evaluations. While current DOA initiatives in the Netherlands are promising, their long-term success will depend on deeper integration into academic culture – through structural support, dedicated funding, and institutional recognition.

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Appendix A: Questionnaire

Section 1: General information

1. Which research university are you affiliated with?
2. What is your current position?
3. What is your gender?
4. What is your field of research?
5. How many publications have you had so far? (books and articles)

Section 2: Knowledge and publishing experience / habits

1. Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?
2. How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?
3. Has your supervisor or faculty encouraged you to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers for books?
4. How important are the following factors in influencing your decision on where to publish your journal articles? Please rate each factor on a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 is 'Not Important' and 10 is 'Very Important'.
5. How important are the following factors in influencing your decision on where to publish your books? Please rate each factor on a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 is 'Not Important' and 10 is 'Very Important'.
6. If you have any other factors influencing your publishing decisions please specify below. (Optional)

Section 3: Publishing in Diamond Open Access venues

1. Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers? (If you are not an early-career researcher, please answer this question from the perspective of a supervisor or mentor.)
2. Do you know if your university offers any support for publishing in the Diamond Open Access model?
3. If you have published or considered publishing a book or an article in Diamond Open Access, what factors influenced your decision? (Select all that apply)

4. What do you perceive as the main barriers for you or for other people to publishing in Diamond Open Access journals? (Select all that apply)
5. What do you perceive as the main barriers for you or other people to publishing books in a Diamond Open Access model? (Select all that apply)
6. What support or resources would help you decide whether to publish in a Diamond Open Access outlet (journal or book)? (Select all that apply)
7. If your university offered support for publishing in a Diamond Open Access journal or book, would you consider using this option?

Section 4: Any additional thoughts on your publishing experience or DOA? (Optional)

1. Would you like to be contacted for more questions regarding your experience with DOA?

Appendix B: Graphs

1. General

2.1. Senior researchers in the social sciences

What is your current position?

How many publications have you had so far? (books and articles)

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

33 Respondents

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

33 Respondents

Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers? (If you are not an early-career researcher, please answer this question from the perspective of a supervisor or mentor.)

32 Respondents

Do you know if your university offers any support for publishing in the Diamond Open Access model?

31 Respondents

2.2 Senior researchers in STEM

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

52 Respondents

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

52 Respondents

Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers? (If you are not an early-career researcher, please answer this question from the perspective of a supervisor or mentor.)

47 Respondents

Do you know if your university offers any support for publishing in the Diamond Open Access model?

47 Respondents

2. 3. Senior researchers in Humanities

How many publications have you had so far? (books and articles)

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

12 Respondents

Has your supervisor or faculty encouraged you to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers for books?

13 Respondents

3.1. Early career researchers in STEM

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

22 Respondents

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

21 Respondents

Has your supervisor or faculty encouraged you to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers for books?

21 Respondents

How important are the following factors in influencing your decision on where to publish your journal articles?

Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers?

20 Respondents

If your university offered support for publishing in a Diamond Open Access journal or book, would you consider using this option?

19 Respondents

3.2. Early career researchers in Social Sciences

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

21 Respondents

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

20 Respondents

Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers?

21 Respondents

Do you know if your university offers any support for publishing in the Diamond Open Access model?

19 Respondents

What do you perceive as the main barriers for you or for other people to publishing in Diamond Open Access journals?

What do you perceive as the main barriers for you or other people to publishing books in a Diamond Open Access model?

3.3. Early career researchers in Humanities

Before this survey, were you familiar with the term "Diamond Open Access (DOA)"?

13 Respondents

How much freedom do you have in choosing where to publish your research?

13 Respondents

Has your supervisor or faculty encouraged you to publish in specific journals or with specific publishers for books?

14 Respondents

How important are the following factors in influencing your decision on where to publish your journal articles?

How important are the following factors in influencing your decision on where to publish your books?

Do you think publishing in a Diamond Open Access model is a suitable option for early-career researchers?

12 Respondents

